

Native Orchids of Manipur

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PART I

INTRODUCTION

Manipur has long been known as a happy hunting-ground for orchid enthusiasts and botanists alike; but as yet, still largely unexplored. Many specimens remain undiscovered by professional botanists. It is generally considered that the Europeans who had arrived here in the 19th century did much of the pioneering work in discovering and realizing the wealth of orchids in Manipur. To name a few of them George Watt (Scottish botanist), Charles Baron Clarke (British botanist), K. Alfred Karl Meebold (German Botanist) and Francis Kingdon-Ward (English Botanist) were the first European botanists who collected orchids from Manipur in between 1881-1948. While reporting about *Debrobium cariniferum*, William J. Hooker writes, “The specimen came with a collection of orchids from Dr. Watt, F.L.S., of the Education department of India, whilst attached to a mission engaged on the boundary survey of the kingdom of Munipore, on the eastern frontier of British India, a country previously quite unknown botanically.” About the richness of Manipur’s flora and orchids, Dr. Watt writes, “I cannot enumerate all the bushes and herbs seen in these forests; ferns and

Eria vittata Lindl. Fig. 1

dwarf palms form a dense under-vegetation, while every bough overhead carries its profusion of epiphytic orchids.” Again Dr. Watt, writing in *Nature*, says that nothing in Manipur struck him so much, as a botanist, as the remarkable transition of vegetation in this small region. In 1888, George Watt presented a paper entitled “The Forest of Manipur” while previously in 1887 Charles Baron Clarke presented a paper “On the Flora of Munipore and Kohima” which are valuable works on the flora of Manipur providing descriptions of several new species.

But one cannot deny that the traditional conservators of orchids in Manipur were its native people who not only merely identify them, but also conserved them through their appreciation of its aesthetic value. For centuries the native people have interwoven their intimacy of ecology and taxonomy of the orchids with different aspects of their cultures and rituals. The aim of this series is twofold. The first aim is to introduce to the readers; the intimacy and the significance of orchids in Manipuri culture. The second aim is to examine the literatures as well as providing the description and measurement of each native orchid endemic to Manipur, based on the living plants and herbarium materials.

ORCHIDS IN MANIPURI CULTURE

In the past young men of Moirang principality compete with one another in pursuit of discovering new and rare flowers and orchids as part of the annual ritual called *Thangjing Haraoba*. An instance of a well-defined procedure for giving a newly discovered orchid species a name is mentioned in the *Lei hekpa* (flower picking), *Lei yengba* (Flower showering) *Lei langba* (lt. flower sensing/ feeling after Soyam Lokendrajit translation), *Leirol* (saga of flowers) cantons of the epic of Khamba and Thoibi. Mr. G.H. Damant translated these cantons in gist in 1877 as under:

“... all the people assembled and obtained leave from the king to hold a festival in honor of the god Thangjing and Kongyamba was appointed to collect flowers to decorate the lower division of the village, and Khamba to do the same for the upper division, and Nongbal Chouba then introduced him to the king. Early next morning Kongyamba and Khamba went to pick flowers, as the festival was to be held on the following day. Kongyamba told Khamba to go up the mountain, and he would remain where he was; and Kongyanba picked

haukeroi flowers, but Khamba climbed a tree and gather *mellai* (orchid) flowers, and when they had done so they both returned home... When the king and all the people were assembled for the festival, Kongyamba presented flowers to the deity and the king, and distributed the rest among the people, and Khamba did the same; and the king, seeing that the flowers he had brought were out of season, gave Khamba a reward.”

The persons who took part in this flower surveying ritual were known as “*Lei Langba*”. Just picking and offering the flowers to the god and the king was not enough. The *lei langba* would again deliver the morphological description of the flowers or orchids in present of the king. This procedure was traditionally known as *Leirol* (saga of flower). Thus, a new species was given a name. There is also one manuscript on 108 flowers, including orchids, known as “*Leirol Lambuba*” written by one Hijam Rupa Singh in the 18th-19th century. There is also a saga on flowers known as “*Leirol*” which is believed to be composed by King Charairongba in the 18th century.

Orchids in Manipur may also symbolize power in social stratification. In an autumn divination ritual called *Kwak tanba* (chasing the crow) the head-wears of the royals and nobles were embellished with blue Vanda orchid flowers. In their usual unceremonial fashion also, the kings and nobles decorated their turban with orchids. It is worth mentioning here the eye-witness account of Mrs. St. Clair Grimwood from her memoir published in 1891:

“The Maharajah (Surchandra) was a short, fat, ugly little man, with a face something between that of a Burmese and a Chinaman- rather fairer than the Bengal natives, but much scarred with small-pox. He was dressed very simple in white- a white coat with gold buttons, and a very fine white muslin Dhotee. He had a large white turban on his head, in which was stuck a spray of yellow orchids...”

He (General Thangal) was an old man, nearer eighty than seventy I should think, taller than the average Manipuri, and marvelously active for his age. He had a fine old face, much lined and wrinkled with age and the cares of state which had fallen upon him when he was quite a young

(A) A flowering plant (B) Seed Pod (C) Petals
 (D) Inflorescence (E) Sheath (F) Flower
 (G) Purplish strips (H) Column (I) Pseudobulbs
 (J) Lateral Sepals (K) Lip (L) Side view of flower
 (M) Dorsal sepal (N) Pseudobulbs and leaves
 (O) Leaves (dorsal and ventral side) (P) Anther Cap

man, and had in nowise lessened as his years increased. He had piercing black eyes, shaggy overhanging white eyebrows, and white hair. His nose was long and slightly hooked, and his mouth was finely cut and very determined. He was fond of bright colours, and I never remember seeing him in anything but a delicate pink silk dhotee, a dark coat made from a first-rate English pattern, and a pink turban, and when the orchids were in bloom, he seldom appeared without a large spray of some gorgeous-hued specimen in the top of his turban.”

Orchids also took on a more characteristically role as a season marker in Manipur. One notable example was that in the 15th century the king of Pong proposed to Kyamba, the king of Manipur for a joint military expedition in the Kabo valley. It was agreed that both the forces of the two kingdoms would come to an appointed place for the expedition when the orchid, *Khongam Melei* (*Dendrobium chrysotoxum*) bloomed. The orchid bloomed one month ahead in the kingdom of Pong. So the force of Manipur came one month late.

Thus, all the orchids traditionally identified by the native people carry weighty symbolism in Manipuri culture.

The present article tries to illustrate late winter to spring blooming fragrant orchid species *Eria vittata* found in Manipur.

Eria vittata Lindl., belongs to a section of *Eria* which is characterized by slightly curved terete pseudobulbs. This species is reported from South China and the Himalayas, including Assam and Manipur, and also Northern Thailand. Its common name is the Stripped *Eria* after its stripes on sepals and petals. It is a sympodial orchid growing as epiphyte and lithophyte. Its synonym is *Pinalia vittata* (Lindl). Kuntze.

HISTORY

This species was first reported by Dr. Lindley in his work, Contributions to Indian Orchidology. Vol. II, 1858 (Journal of the Proceedings of the Linnean Society, Botany, Vol.II, London, 1858) in a very short description as “Flowers larger than the last, pale green with crimson stripes ; Lip the same colour, but paler.”

The background of Dr. Lindley’s work on *Eria vittata* is also clearly described by the foremost German Orchidologist Heinrich Gustav Reichenbach in the British horticulture periodical “Gardens Chronicle and New Horticulturist in March, 1882 as under:

“This species has oblong cylindrical or oblong fusiform bulbs with some furrows, and reaches 4-5 inches in length. The two leaves are more than membranaceous, verging to thin fleshy, being very soft, as in *Eria stellata*. The shape is cuneate oblong-lanceolate acute.

The lateral raceme is not many flowered. The green hairless flowers have the sepals, petals, lip, and even the column adorned with red stripes. The oblong crenulate lip has five plaited lamellae, which are edged with red. The column has a square projection on each side. The flowers are equal in size to those of *Eria profusa* Lindl. This is a most remarkable curiosity from a botanical point of view. Till now the plant was only known from Catheart’s drawings, prepared in Sikkim Himalaya by Indian artists, and lent by Sir J. (then Dr.) Hooker to Dr. Lindley, who described the plant from the drawing in his second Contributions to Indian Orchidology. I feel quite persuaded that the plant at hand is the same as that described, for it corresponds in all details.”

DESCRIPTION:

All the photographs of *Eria Vittata* Lindl. in this article were shot with a Sony a6400 fitted with a Sigma 30mm lens with macro extension tube. Measurements and description were made on live material of the species from Churachandpur District, Manipur flowering in January 2020.

The plant is glabrous. Pseudobulbs, 10 cm long, are cylindrical enveloped by brown sheath bearing two leaves, 27 cm long and 6 cm wide, at the apex. The leaf blades are elliptic to elliptic-lanceolate. Inflorescence is pendulous and it looks as if it rises between the leaves, but it emerges

below the subtending leaf as shown in fig. 2. The colour of the flowers (both sepals and petals) is light sage green. Flower diameter is 2.5 cm. There are three sepals, one dorsal (13 mm) and two lateral (13 mm) each with three purplish brown strips and bold border. There are two petals (12 mm). The lip is oblong in outline. Column 1.5 mm, two purplish strips and bold border, with anther cap.

